

1ST NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON RISK MANAGEMENT
"Role of Risk Managers in Attaining a Resilient ASEAN Community"
December 13-15, 2017
PANGASINAN STATE UNIVERSITY, LINGAYEN PANGASINAN
Prepared by: Domenic T. Sanchez

DAY ONE (Dec.13, 2017)

It was a long but memorable journey of nature's beauty and scenery that captured my sense of appreciation of God's creation on our way from Cebu to Lingayen. I, Mr. Domenic Sanchez, and my companion Mr. Francis Val Gamboa, were fortunate to be chosen as the CTU

Naga Extension Campus representatives to attend the 1st National Conference on Risk Management on December 13-15, 2017, at Pangasinan State University. According to the PSU President's message, the said conference is an excellent opportunity to share knowledge and

experience on how each Filipino can respond and cope with a few of the most significant challenges in human existence – environmental-related disasters, technology risk, safety, and security concerns. This conference is aligned with the long-term vision for the Philippines' future, as embodied in Ambisyon 2040, towards a

high-trust society where families thrive in vibrant, culturally diverse, and resilient communities. He commended the Association of Risk Managers of The Philippines (ARMP) Inc. for spearheading the conduct of the said activity that seeks to remind everyone of the importance of the task to build Philippine society's resilience and protect the country and its people from future disasters. Such remarks paved the way for the opening of the event.

Police Officer 3, Rodulfo Naumlayan, gave his rationale for the topic that he would discuss after being introduced to the audience. The following are personal safety, home safety, child safety, workplace safety, vehicle safety, vacation safety, anti-theft, holiday safety, anti-carnapping, bomb threat dos and don'ts, threat detection and assessment, modus operandi, and rape prevention tips. For personal safety, he stressed out that one has to be wary of suspicious persons around. We have to be sensitive to signs of threat arising from our personal and official circumstances. Bad elements are always sneaking around, finding ways to victimize people they found to be carefree and unaware.

According to him, life is more precious than material possession; in the case of hold up, he advised us not to fight back but instead give what the thief wants. To preserve life which is too precious, than or money the cellphone should be a priority. Stolen possession can be acquired again, unlike life with no second chance once it is taken from us. Immediately alert the

authorities once the suspect has left. Make sure to remember his physical description for proper profiling and identification. Also, he reminded us to avoid observable behavior patterns, which would enable a potential attacker to predict a person's future movements, construct a plan based on it, intercept that person and isolate him from any assistance. Do not stay overnight in places with which help is not possible, just in case. He also mentioned the things necessary for home safety, like the control of keys in your residence. Never allow someone to borrow or use your keys, especially an acquaintance because he might have your keys duplicated, and he may burglarize your property during your absence or trip. This is very common, according to him, in some house helpers. With the wrong trust, the mistake of such may lead to theft without difficulty because the perpetrator already has the key. That is why he strongly reminded everyone not to entrust keys to others. Should you lose a key, immediately replace or change the cylinder lock. Using the strong door and steel bars would greatly help

against intruders. After he discussed all the sub-topics, PO3 Naumlayan was given a plaque of recognition.

At 11 A.M., Honorable Maria Cielo Grace M. Padaca, a former broadcast journalist for fourteen years. She has been the Governor of the Province of Isabela from 2004 to 2010 and a Commissioner of the COMELEC from 2012-2014. With her resilient leadership, she was a recipient of the 2008 Ramon Magsaysay Award for Government Service for empowering Isabela voters to reclaim their democratic right to suffrage and contribute as full partners in development. Her calling as a public servant continued when she co-founded Kaya Natin: A movement for good governance and ethical leadership with Eddie Panlilio and the late Jesse Robredo. Grace Padaca shared her thoughts about being a PWD or Person with a disability as she advocates good governance and effective service delivery. The disability did not hinder her from serving the people of Isabela. She never dreamed of becoming a politician. But destiny calls when there was no one to run as an opposition to a well-known political dynasty. She was bullied and ridiculed for her incapability. What can a disabled person like her do in governance anyway? But that did not discourage her from pushing through her advocacy. During that time, there was rampant illegal logging in Isabela. Fortunately, she won the election, and as the newly elected Governor, she had immediately put it to stop. She made it. A social responsibility that the former political dynasty and its cohorts with their strongly-abled legs did nothing and gave way for illegal logging to proliferate. What have they done while in power? She mentioned that we were in the crucial times that calamities are expected not to be more strong but also more frequent. The environmental dangers we face now will be "lalakas, dadalas, titindi" like typhoons, floods, drought etc. Financial threats and technical threats are becoming sophisticated; that is why we have to be proactive. We should not leave everything to the

government. Each one must do his share in order to find ways, if not totally stop at once, the cause of man-made calamities being escalated by the natural ones. Flood is one example of a natural disaster; however, this can be devastating if we do not stop illegal logging and destroy our forests. She encouraged everyone, especially us risk managers, to be vigilant. After her sharing, an open forum followed, in which she entertained questions from the audience. It concluded the morning session. A sumptuous lunch took place after that.

Ms. Rizalyn A. Capanas facilitated the afternoon plenary session. She then introduced the next resource speaker, who happened to be the President and CEO/CTO, Datamobility Corporation. When implementing the DHL Philippines system, Mr. Michael Angelo D. Maske started data line Philippines back in 1991 and pioneered the Surfing and Browsing approach. His company developed Campus++, a school management system, and later incorporated as

Datapacific Corporation in 2004 and 2016, re-incorporated to Datamobility Corporation. Mr. Maske designed and created parentUpp, the Philippines' first multi-school parenting mobile application that addresses "absentee parenting" His app recently won the UN World Summit Awards for Southeast Asia for best practice in using ICTs for social impact in Singapore. He used to have product presentations and demonstrations, but he discussed risk management and mitigating risk using cloud-based solutions this afternoon. According to him, cloud-based technology seems to be not common to all, but there is risk associated with it in making decisions and procuring technologies. How to mitigate technology risk using the cloud-based solution? This has something to do with cloud storage and the risks of the data being stored. A cloud subscription model that may be storage of important data, for instance in school, like

grades, payroll, employee profile, financial statement etc. He discussed about technology and trend and the use of app.

The next resource speaker was Wilson W. Censon, the Project Development Officer of the Department of Information and Communications Technology Field Operations Office for Cluster 2 in Luzon. He is a co-founder of the mobile IT for Youth prevalently known as Mobility from 2014 up to the present. With his co-founding of Mobility, current situations, workforce and tools of the IT Industry in the Philippines are being discussed in the various schools within the region. He is one of the most sought resource persons on Current Issues and Trends in

Information
Communicati
ons
Technology,
Cyber
Security
Awareness,
Visual
Computer
Programmin
g, and the
Internet. He
discussed the
government

projects/programs to address technology and the salient provisions of the proposed social media policy for the government. He also discussed administrative orders such as account management, guidelines for civil servants, security, social media activity monitoring, social media education administrative accountability. He also mentioned the National Cyber Security Plan of 2022, which aims to protect the nation, its government and private infrastructures,

small-medium enterprises, large businesses, and corporations, etc. Atty. Faustino Madriaga Jr., The chairman of the Board of Trustees of la Consolacion College and the Corporate Secretary and Legal Consultant of the Diocesan Schools of

the Roman Catholic Bishop of Novaliches Educational System, Roman Catholic Archbishop of Manila, Order of Franciscan Minors, Capuchins, AVS Group of Companies, Manila Wilferrous Builders Inc., Diocesan Schools of San Fernando, La Union, and various reputable academic organizations like Asian Institute of Management, Reedley International School, Southville International College, and Don Bosco School-Manila. He served as the Dean of the College of Law of Polytechnic College of La Union, from 2009 to 2013 and has been sharing his expertise on Education laws at Ateneo De Manila University from 2010 up to the present. A member of Integrated Bar of the Philippines and Philippine Association of Voluntary Arbitrators and the Chairman of Sambayan Educational Foundation, Inc.

According to him, each should be an active participant in minimizing, reducing, and eliminating the effects of risks. Risks always have their negative connotation. Every day as we wake up, the risk is already around. We are all exposed to threats, even in sleep. He acknowledged Mr. Marke's presentation about the Cloud subscription technology and Mr.

Centso's since their topics were so much related in his. He stressed out the hard facts about the Data Privacy Act, which was enacted and approved on August 15, 2012, which purpose is to protect the fundamental human right of privacy of

communication while ensuring free flow of information to promote innovation and growth. The Act applies to the processing of all types of personal information. Do schools collect or process information from students? Its employees, its faculty, parents?. If the answer is yes, then, therefore, these data are under the scope of the Data Privacy Act. Personal information is any information recorded in a material form or not, from which the identity of an individual is apparent or can be reasonably and directly ascertained by the entity holding the information, or when put together with other information, would directly and certainly identify an individual. Processing is any operation performed upon personal information. These pieces of information are dealt with by controllers like the teachers, HR personnel etc., who collect, hold, process or use personal information in connection with the individual's personal, family, and household affairs. Aside from personal information, there is this so-called sensitive personal information. What is Sensitive Personal Information? It is about an individual's race, ethnic origin, marital status, age, color, religious, philosophical or political affiliation. It also likewise

covers the individual's health, education, genetic or sexual life of a person, or to any processing for any offense committed or alleged to have been committed by such person, the disposal of such proceedings or sentence of any court in such proceedings. He stressed out that if the controller directly or indirectly divulges these pieces of information, it is a clear violation of a person's sensitive personal information. Section 20 of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 clearly states that the personal information controller should keep confidential and secure all personal information. Sec. 25 states that authorized processing of personal information has the punishment of imprisonment of 1 to 3 years and a fine of Php500,00 to Php2 million. The unauthorized processing of sensitive personal information would send someone to imprisonment in 1-6 years and a lofty penalty of Php500,000 to Php4 million. Sec. 26 states that accessing personal information by negligence has a punishment of 1-3 years imprisonment and a fine of Php500,000 to Php2 million. And lastly, sec. 27 punishes someone of 6 months to 1-

year imprisonment and a fine of Php100,000 to Php500,000 for improper disposal of personal information. The National Privacy Commission is an independent

body attached to the Dept. of Information and Communication. It issued implementing rules and regulations of the Data Privacy Act on August 24, 2016. Act He reminded us all that there is no such thing as private in the internet. All information on the internet is prone to hacking and intrusion. However, it is ironic that most people give so much personal information on social media like Facebook than any other printed platform. Every person has Rights to data Subject, according to sec. 34, such as the right to be informed, right to object, right to access, right to correct, right to rectification, erasure, or blocking. After the lengthy discussion of the good attorney, many audience members were eager to participate in the open forum. Each speaker had to entertain two questions, but it came out that the lawyer resource speaker got most of the questions. Only one or two inquired from the IT resource speakers.

On the evening of December 13, 2017, A sumptuous dinner was served to the participants during the socialization night. The participants were entertained by the talents of Pangasinan State University, both its faculty members and students.

Photo opportunity with Dr. Susana L. Fernandez, President of ARMP

DAY TWO (Dec. 14, 2017)

Steve F. Dailisan is an award-winning news producer of GMA news tv, the leading and trusted news organization in the Philippines. Steve's hard work, dedication, and passion for the craft earned him noteworthy recognitions such as the 1st Leaf Award on Media in 2013, World Silver Medalist at the 2014 New York

Festival for his documentary, Outstanding Filipino Journalist in 2015, 2016, and 2017 Indieng Indie Festival Most Trusted Media Personality. Apart from delivering news and information, he has been constantly involved with community-related projects and activities, making him a Gintong Kabataan Awardee in 2014. Steve discussed the Role of Media in Disaster Management. According to him, the role of media BEFORE, DURING, and AFTER every man-made and natural calamity is vital. "Before" is a matter of forecasting. It gives sense to all to

prepare for the incoming typhoon, for instance. What if there is no media informing people in the possible areas prone to flood or landslide? There may be many deaths and destruction in the absence of contingency action without the information provided by the media. Information nowadays can be accessed through

different platforms. We have the internet, TV, prints, radio. In addition, GMA launched the IM Ready app for the latest update of the weather or the location of the typhoon. "Before" is essential because it is when we prepare for a calamity. "During" is another thing. During the onset of Yolanda, all preparation seemed to be ineffective because no one would expect how intense and destructive that super typhoon. The death toll rose. Many lost their homes and even loved ones. Now, what was the role of media then? With the help of media, aid and was provided at once. The most critical part of Tacloban was located, and immediate medical and relief assistance was on the way for the people. "After" is likewise as important as the two because, through the non-stop flow of information, help is now for the recovering people and rebuilding their lives. And then he showed us his footage when super typhoon Yolanda hit the Visayas, particularly in Tacloban and Ormoc. It was a heartbreaking experience to see the degree of damage as if hope is nowhere to be found. Lives and properties both washed out. Death and hunger were everywhere. The viewing ended his sharing that morning.

Regina "Gina Paz Lopez is a strong advocate of children and education, the environment and its protection, as well as health and wellness. Ms. Gina spearheaded the Bantay Bata 163, a child welfare program, and led the reforestation of La Mesa Watershed and La Mesa Ecopark and the Rehabilitation of the Pasig River. She became the Secretary of Environment and Natural resources in 2016 and had issued closure orders for 22 mine sites because of the risks they posed to the community. Building the Country from Bottom Up is her current advocacy after her appointment as DENR secretary was denied of her due to a lot of intrigues and criticism from the political opposition whose mining businesses were compromised during her time in office. She said that there are so many ways of helping people. One way is to uplift their lives before building their homes. She mentioned the fate of those areas which Yolanda heavily damaged in 2013. She showed pictures of people whose lives were transformed after being renovated, restructured, and converted to eco-tourism destinations. She said that the

foundation of genuine economic growth is love. The greatest manifestation of love is the area development for the people and the environment committed to integrity and ecological harmony. Love is decency. People learn to live and hope again once their lives are changed, their area is changed. For instance, a

depressed area that she once sat foot somewhere in Metro Manila had the highest crime rate. Looking at the area, it was dirty and out of order. So what she did was to dialogue with the different leaders and initiate a clean-up drive involving the whole community. Then later, the people themselves were the ones who preserve their environment, making it wholesome and livable for everyone. There was also a literacy program for children and out-of-school youth. There was livelihood training for the adults. The project was successful; the crime rate in that area diminished to zero because people there were given the opportunity to change their lives and way of living. Dole-outs and giving of goods are not sufficient. One has to look into changing the lives of people for them to change as well. Love is a commitment to integrity. Love is Ecological Harmony. Love is compassionate entrepreneurship. Love is working together in a convergent manner. Gina had shown us her different successful projects all over the Philippines. One of those is the Ugong Rock. It was then a poor community raping the

environment but living around a spectacular 18 million-year rock formation. 98% of the community are women. Only two graduated from college. Most did not even finish high school. When they were educated about the damage they did to the environment, they became the catalyst of change. In the year 2008, the community income was only Php7, 150.00 with the destruction of their very own flora and fauna. Like doing the slash-and-burn practice of farming and hunting of animals. In 2009 it became 133,800.00 until it reached 29,968,341.35 million as their annual income on tourism and many products from the environment that once they abused and took advantage. People in Ugong Rock are now happy.

She also shared to us the sad truth about how the government turned a blind eye to the capability of our scientists to produce cheaper medicine from our very

own endemic plants. These plants, according to her, were pirated and patented in other countries and got imported again in the Philippines with higher prices. Such as Nata de Coco, which is patented in Japan. Ampalaya under vitamin A-rich vegetable is already patented in the USA. Ampalaya mixed with eggplant as a cure of diabetes is patented by Cromack Research, Inc. in New Jersey, USA. The Philippine Yew Tree (*Taxus Sumatrana*), a source of taxol, a cancer-curing substance, has been patented by the University of Philadelphia. Ylang-ylang, a source of perfume, is now exported to Europe, now owned by Yves St.Laurent. The Philippine sea snail (*Conus magus*), a source of the toxin, called SNX 111, a pain killer 1000 times more powerful than morphine, now patented by Neurex Corp., as the US company purchased by Elan Corp. in Iceland. Banaba, a treatment for fever, diarrhea, diabetes, and as a purgative and stimulant, is now patented by a Japanese Company Itoen KK. Saluyot or Jute, an anti-stress tablet, is mass-produced and processed into powder in the Philippines by a Japanese firm. Sambong, Lagundi, and Takipkuhol (*Centella Asiatica*), have been the subject of many patent claims by Japanese companies. We are getting robbed of what we have, yet the government has not done anything about it. It is our ancestral, cultural property.

Ms. Gina then told us to sing with her this song as she ended her talk.

WE NEED TO WAKE UP
WE NEED TO WISE UP
WE NEED TO OPEN OUR EYES AND DO IT NOW, NOW, NOW
WE NEED TO BUILD A BETTER FUTURE AND
WE NEED TO START RIGHT NOW

WE'RE ON A PLANET THAT HAS A PROBLEM
WE HAVE TO SOLVE IT, GET INVOLVED, AND DO IT NOW, NOW, NOW
WE NEED TO BUILD A BETTER FUTURE AND
WE NEED TO START RIGHT NOW (2X)

An open forum followed right away.

The afternoon session was the Lecture about Basic Safety and Life Support by the Philippine Red Cross/PDDRM/AF-Philippine Army. The speaker talked about the earthquake. According to him that 80 percent of quakes would occur at the rim of the Pacific Ocean, particularly in the Ring of Fire. The Ring of Fire covers regions with 452 volcanoes. 75 percent of active and dormant volcanoes. The earthquake has caused both active and dormant volcanoes

to erupt. Undersea earthquakes cause tsunami along with coastal areas. There are 500,000 detectable earthquakes every year, 100,000 of which can be felt only, and 100 are known to be devastating. An earthquake has caused 8,000 to 10,000 deaths

every year. It can exude an intensity of 100 times stronger than the atomic bombs in Hiroshima. Normally, it is not the shaking of the ground that would cause death but the falling debris, fire, landslide, and tsunami. The best practice during the occurrence of an earthquake is to stay calm and do not panic. Do the DROP, COVER, and HOLD ON. He also discussed some important guidelines during an earthquake, like staying away from cabinets, bookshelves, and other things that may fall during the tremor. If you have a child with you, carry him while doing the cover, duck, and hold. If possible, cover the child and protect him as you do. Transform fear into action, do not panic, stay calm, and have common sense at all times. Pullover to a safe area, do the drop, cover, and hold if you are driving. Stay away from overpasses, bridges, flyovers, and electrical posts. Stay away from the elevated area, for it might collapse during the quake. If you are near the coastal line, secure yourself to higher sturdy ground, a tsunami might come anytime. For persons with disabilities, go to the safest area near the foundation or the wall and do the drop, cover and hold. If in the building, do not use the elevator. IN CASE OF AN EARTHQUAKE, RUN FOR COVER BEFORE FACEBOOKING ABOUT IT. Life is more important than getting famous in a tragedy. Most earthquakes would last a minute or less, but aftershocks can follow an earthquake on and off for days or weeks. And lastly, he reminded us all that nothing beats regular training. The training proves to be the key ingredient to handling any disaster. Chances favor the well-prepared.

Later we were group into 3. The group would be the MEDICAL TEAM, SECURITY TEAM, TRAFFIC/COMMUNICATION TEAM, and RESCUE TEAM. I happened to be part of the Rescue Team. Our team leader from Zamboanga refreshed us regarding the different types of carries since we were tasked to rescue injured individuals in a simulation earthquake drill. We actualized each carry. There was also color-coding of injured individuals. ORANGE means slightly injured, RED means severely injured, and BLACK means casualty or dead person.

After the briefing, there was the ringing of the alarm. We did the drop, cover, and hold. Some of the participants hid underneath the tables. Some stood still against the wall and foundations. After the alarm, everybody got up and went outside to do the tasks. The spotter caught our attention as rescuers. She found a supposed injured girl. I was the first in the area, so I looked at her and asked her if she could stand. She cried; although I knew she was just faking it, I have to consider the scene realistic. There was blood, and her hand was cut. She trembled and begged for help. So I called an assistant to carry her. Good thing that another rescuer came by, so we did a three-man's carry and brought her to the nearby medical outpost. Another boy was spotted to have a supposed injury in his belly. Blood was all over his mid-section. I asked him if he could stand and walk with me. He nodded, so I performed a one-man assist and led him to the medical post. The third one spotted was lying motionless. He could be dead, so a stretcher was secured to carry his remains immediately. And then the last victim hid in the building; if not of the bystander's call he could not be found. He was severely injured and

cannot move, so we used a stretcher and carried him to the medical team. In general, there were roughly seven injured students at the scene of an earthquake drill. One noteworthy thing was to notice students who were not part of the drill but went to the open ground for safety as they heard the alarm. I was informed that the school always conducts earthquake and fire drills to get used to it already. Our team leader congratulated me,

and the commanding-in-chief tap my shoulder for my quick response and a job well done. It was everybody's success. And the dirt and sweat all over me were worth it. That activity concluded our day. I thanked the participative PSU students for their cooperation. And by the way, the blood-like substance, according to them, was just a mixture of water, starch, and food coloring. Now I knew.

DAY THREE (Dec. 15, 2017)

EDUCATIONAL TOUR/VISIT TO HUNDRED ISLANDS NATIONAL PARK

WATER SEARCH AND RESCUE (WASAR)

Thank You CTU and Pangasinan State University, Shalom!